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reSEArch-EU

SPIN-OFF COMPETENCE LAB TRAINING PROGRAMME

DELIVERABLE 3.3

(DUE TO M33, SEPTEMBER 2023)

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Deliverable Identification

Deliverable No. and Title	D 3.3 Spin-off Competence Lab training programme
Leader	Dr. Laura Martin
Related task(s)	Task 3.5
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Dissemination level	Public
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Submission	29/09/2023
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Duration	36 months
<p>The aim of this task was to improve and support an entrepreneurial mindset and entrepreneurial competences among scientists in a two-step process to increase and exploit the potential of entrepreneurial ideas and initiatives.</p> <p>The first step was achieved by the development of a competence laboratory dedicated to early-stage researchers and offering virtual training - on the social media of the SEA-EU and the reSEArch-EU projects and up-skilling on 'future-proof' competencies including problem-solving, self-management and entrepreneurship capabilities as well as soft skills and</p>	

emotional intelligence. Second, existing local university facilities specialised in supporting entrepreneurial initiatives and start-ups serve as a link between the Spin-off Competence Lab and entrepreneurial enabled scientists by providing integrated follow up services and support.

Versions and Contributions History

Version	Date	Modified by	Reason
1.	25.09.2023	Mariia Iamkovaia	Presentation of the deliverable to the IPCC
1.	29.09.2023	Mariia Iamkovaia	Presentation of the deliverable to the EEC

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this work was to improve and support an entrepreneurial mindset and competences among scientists in a two-step process to increase and exploit the potential of entrepreneurial ideas and initiatives. This task extends and complements the objectives of Task 4.5 (Work-based engagement and entrepreneurial mindset) of the SEA-EU E+ project, focused on students of the Alliance. The first step was achieved by the development of a competence laboratory dedicated to early-stage researchers and offering virtual training - on the platform of SEA-EU Academy developed in WP2 and upskilling on 'future-proof' competencies including problem-solving, self-management, and entrepreneurship capabilities as well as soft skills and emotional intelligence. It will take the form of a set of workshops/webinars addressed to early-stage researchers led by experts from both academia and industry, business professionals (including stakeholders of the SEA-INNOVATE HUB, Task 3.4), start-up founders (e.g., as role models for entrepreneurial success cases) and university experts in entrepreneurship, intellectual property rights (IPR) and innovation management. The number and content of workshops was adapted to the needs identified through the virtual competence survey. Second, existing local university facilities specialized in supporting entrepreneurial initiatives and start-ups serve as a link between the Spin-Off Competence Lab and entrepreneurial enabled scientists by providing integrated follow-up services and support. By integrating these complementary structures and services, newly emerging entrepreneurial ideas initiated by the Lab's transfer of competence can be further promoted and supported in their development into spin-offs and start-ups. Spin-Off Competence Lab, through an interdisciplinary approach and innovative models of engagement, learning, and communication, acted as a catalyst, breeder, and promoter of both culture and knowledge for entrepreneurship and innovation.

2. IDENTIFICATION OF THE WORK NAME

- Deliverable: D3.3 Spin-Off Competence Lab training program (M33)

Figure 1. Poster of Spin-Off Competence Lab

3. EXPECTATIONS AT THE BEGINNING OF THE PROJECT

- What does the Description of Action establish in reference to this action?

This initiative aimed to create and encourage entrepreneurial mindsets and capabilities among scientists through a two-step process, increasing and maximising the potential of entrepreneurial ideas and actions.

1) The first phase was devoted to the creation of an educational program for alliance university students under the umbrella of the SEA-EU E+ initiative. This phase was intended to be accomplished through the creation of a dedicated competence lab for early-stage researchers, providing virtual training (via the SEA-EU Academy platform developed in WP2) and the enhancement of "future-proofing" competencies such as problem-solving, self-management, and entrepreneurship skills, as well as interpersonal and emotional intelligence.

Subsequently, it was going to take the shape of a series of workshops and webinars geared toward early-stage researchers, led by **academic** and **industrial experts**, **business practitioners** (i.e., stakeholders from the SEA-INNOVATE HUB (Task 3.4)), **start-up founders** (such as business success models), and **university experts in entrepreneurship**, Intellectual Property Rights (**IPR**), and **innovation management**.

2) The second stage was the formation of integrated follow-up services and supports, local university facilities that specialize in fostering entrepreneurial ventures and start-ups provide a bridge between the Spin-Off Competence Lab and entrepreneurially

equipped scientists. The Lab's transfer of competence can further promote and support the growth of freshly emerging entrepreneurial ideas into spin-offs and start-ups by integrating these complementary structures and services. The Spin-Off Competence Lab served as a catalyst, breeder, and promoter of both culture and knowledge for entrepreneurship and innovation through an interdisciplinary approach and cutting-edge forms of engagement, learning, and communication.

- Why did your university consider it relevant in writing the project proposal?

For the alliance university students and researchers, these entrepreneur training exercises are essential for numerous reasons:

1. Foster innovation: Mindsets that are entrepreneurial encourage innovation, creativity, and innovative problem-solving. The main idea was to inspire university students and young investigators to generate original new ideas and answers to problems in the real world by teaching them how to think creatively with a focus on business development.

2. Adaptability and resilience: To succeed as entrepreneurs, people need to be able to adjust and persevere through some difficulties. Students who are taught to think like entrepreneurs acquire a mindset that welcomes change, takes lessons from mistakes, and perseveres in the pursuit of their objectives.

3. Economic growth and competitiveness: Entrepreneurship is essential for promoting economic growth and boosting a nation's ability to compete internationally. We can promote a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship that promotes economic development by encouraging entrepreneurial mindsets among the alliance university students and researchers.

4. Problem-solving and social impact: Entrepreneurs frequently recognize and respond to unmet social needs. The Spin-Off Competence Lab course is dedicated to motivating young researchers to recognize social, environmental, and economic concerns and find creative solutions to address them by empowering them with an entrepreneurial attitude. This method has a good impact on society and aids in addressing urgent problems in sectors including sustainability, education, environmental protection, and poverty reduction.

- What was your vision back then regarding this action?

The work development was acquired in a variety of forms during the meetings of the work team to brainstorm ideas and concepts. The final several options were chosen to provide the best possible way to accomplish the set-up goals of the work. These two developed plans were composed of a basic option and a premium one.

The basic option was developed based on the general requirements of the project proposal and it is composed of:

- Five partners (all except UBO).
- Ten webinars, two for each partner.
- Organizing monthly webinars between September 2022 and June 2023.
- Every webinar will be live-streamed on the YouTube channel of the SEA-EU project and then uploaded to the SEA-EU Academy and SEA INNOVATIVE HUB virtual platforms for further dissemination.

The premium option includes a more advanced educational program far beyond the project proposal, which is more ambitious but also unattainable with the budget available in reSEArch-EU. The premium program embraces:

- One- or two-week long virtual courses to be produced by each partner for each learning module.
- Each partner will record and produce 10 to 20 short videos (4 to 8 minutes each) for their respective learning module.
- To support the video courses, additional material, self-evaluation forms, and discussion forums will be created.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORK

- Once the project started, how was the activity planned?

Preliminary plan for the entire work phase:

First stage: November 2021 – February 2022:

- Design and completion of virtual surveys on competences, culture, and knowledge about entrepreneurship among the alliance university researchers. For this, questionnaire is intended to identify the needs of early-stage researchers related to entrepreneurship.
- Assessment of current trends and challenges related to entrepreneurship and digital competences.

Second stage: March 2022 – June 2022:

- Design of educational modules and methodologies.
- Dissemination of the designed modules among potential participants among the alliance university partners.
- Uploading of the dissemination materials to the SEA-EU Academies and establishment of dates for the workshops and webinars.

Third stage: October 2022 – June 2023:

- Delivery of planned workshops and webinars.
- Preparation and submission of the complete program of the Spin-Off Competence Laboratory to the European Commission.

The main objectives of the Spin-Off Competence Laboratory:

- Development of a competence virtual laboratory dedicated to early-stage researchers with offers of free training.

- Acquisition of hard skills: business administration and innovation management.
 - Improvement of soft “future-proof” skills: problem-solving, self-management, and entrepreneurial abilities.
- Which was the methodology employed for the completion of this action?

Participatory and collaborative techniques were applied to emphasise the involvement of many stakeholders (alliance partners, in identifying important needs, and in defining the creation and implementation of an action plan). This strategy frequently produces more thorough and effective results because it relies on multiple perspectives and engages individuals who are directly touched by the action. The main elements of this methodology are included as follows:

- Participatory approach entails enlisting a variety of people and organisations with an interest in the project or action. This can include alliance partners, students, young researchers, professionals, organisations, and other stakeholders. Their involvement guarantees that the action plan considers many points of view, requirements, and concerns.
- Collaboration methodology is the process of cooperating with others to accomplish a common objective. It means that the action plan is shaped by the skills, resources, and insights of the stakeholders.
- Determination of fundamental criteria: before beginning any action, it is critical to decide on the key requirements that the action will solve. By integrating multiple stakeholders in this process, it can acquire a more comprehensive picture of the situation and prioritise the most pressing issues.
- The creation and implementation of the work plan: after identifying the needs, stakeholders work together to develop an action plan that addresses those needs. This entails brainstorming, problem-solving, and utilising the members' different expertise and abilities to produce effective tactics.
- Integration and diversification: the participative and collaborative approach guarantees that varied perspectives are taken into account, avoiding any biases and gaps in understanding. Incorporating a range of perspectives results in a more well-rounded and comprehensive action plan.
- Adaptability: joint efforts can result in strategies that are more flexible and able to adapt when conditions change and stakeholders provide feedback in real time. This adaptability increases the likelihood of success, even in unpredictable environments.
- Openness and interaction: promoting understanding and consensus-building among stakeholders through open communication. Participant trust is fostered via open communication and transparent decision-making.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1. Survey of the entrepreneurial skills of our research communities. Creation of the draft survey

Following a participatory methodology, a survey was deployed focusing on the following questions: entrepreneurial competences, intellectual property protection, entrepreneurial tools, and innovation competences. The main objective of the survey was to identify the self-perceived educational needs and understanding of the target group (i.e., young scientists in the alliance universities). This knowledge allowed us to prepare the most comprehensive Spin-Off Competence Laboratory program which will meet the needs of the mentioned target group.

The design of the questionnaire was completed by EntreComp European framework. This European framework highlights the cross-disciplinary skills that make up an entrepreneurial mindset. These skills can be utilized to enhance entrepreneurial learning in a variety of contexts, including corporations, Small and Mid-size Enterprises (SME) and startup businesses, civil society, the social economy, education, and youth work, as well as in the community and, more broadly, as individuals and citizens. Entrepreneurship skills are becoming more widely regarded as transferable life skills that are important for career advancement, personal growth, and starting new projects including community campaigns, social enterprises, and start-up firms ([EntreComp: a practical guide, easing the access to entrepreneurship \(europa.eu\)](#)).

Consequently, EntreComp was applied to develop the questionnaires through the following three stages: 1) Ideas and Opportunities, 2) Resources, 3) Into action (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – EntreComp applied for the survey with three areas: Ideas & Opportunities, Resources, and Into action.

5.1.1 Ideas & Opportunities

COMPETENCE	HINT	DESCRIPTION
1.1 Spotting opportunities	Use your imagination and abilities to identify opportunities for creating value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and seize opportunities to create value by exploring the social, cultural, and economic landscape - Identify needs and challenges that need to be met - Establish new connections and bring together scattered elements of the landscape to create opportunities to create value
1.2 Creativity	Develop creative and purposeful ideas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop several ideas and opportunities to create value, including better solutions to existing and new challenges - Explore and experiment with innovative approaches - Combine knowledge and resources to achieve valuable effects
1.3 Vision	Work towards your vision of the future	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Imagine the future - Develop a vision to turn ideas into action - Visualise future scenarios to help guide effort and action
1.4 Valuing ideas	Make the most of ideas and opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Judge what values is in social, cultural, and economic terms - Recognise the potential in idea has for creating value and identify suitable ways of making the most out of it
1.5 Ethical & sustainable thinking	Assess the consequences and impact of ideas, opportunities, and actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess the consequences of ideas that bring value the effect of entrepreneurial action on the target community, the market, society, and the environment - Reflect on how sustainable long-term social, cultural, and economic goals are, and the course of action chosen - Act responsibly

Comptences per area
IDEAS & OPPORTUNITIES

5.1.2 Resources

Competences per area
RESOURCES

COMPETENCE	HINT	DESCRIPTION
2.1 Self-awareness & self-efficacy	Believe in yourself and keep developing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reflect on your needs, aspirations and wants in the short medium and long term - Identify and assess your individual and group strengths and weaknesses - Believe in your ability to influence the course of events despite uncertainty, setbacks, and temporary failures
2.2 Motivation & perseverance	Stay focused and don't give up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be determined to turn ideas into action and satisfy your need to achieve - Be prepared to be patient and keep trying to achieve your long-term individual or group aims - Be resilient under pressure, adversity, and temporary failure
2.3 Mobilising resources	Gather and manage the resources you need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get and manage the material, non-material and digital resources needed to turn ideas into action - Make the most of limited resources - Get and manage the competences needed at any stage, including technical, legal, tax and digital competences
2.4 Financial & economic literacy	Develop financial and economic know-how	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estimate the cost of turning an idea into a value – creating activity - Plan, put in place and evaluate financial decisions over time - Manage financing to measure your value-creating activity can last over the long term
2.5 Mobilising others	Inspire, enthuse, and get others on board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspire and enthuse relevant stakeholders - Get the support needed to achieve valuable outcomes - Demonstrate effective communication, persuasion, negotiation, and leadership

5.1.3 Into Action

Competence per area
INTO ACTION

COMPETENCE	HINT	DESCRIPTION
3.1 Taking the initiative	Go for it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiate processes that create value - Take up challenges - Act and work independently to achieve goals, stick to intentions and carry out planned tasks
3.2 Planning & management	Prioritise, organise, and follow up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set long, medium, and short-term goals - Define priorities and action plan - Adapt to unforeseen changes
3.3 Coping with uncertainty, ambiguity & risk	Make decisions dealing with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make decisions when the result of that decision is uncertain, when the information available is partial or ambiguous, or when there is a risk of unintended outcomes - Within the value-creating process, include structured ways of testing ideas and prototypes from the early stages, to reduce risks of failing - Handle fast-moving situations promptly and flexible
3.4 Working with others	Team up, collaborate and network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work together and co-operate with others to develop ideas and turn them into action - Network - Solve conflicts and face up to competition positively when necessary
3.5 Learning through experience	Learn by doing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use any initiative for value creation as a learning opportunity - Learn with others, including peers and mentors - Reflect and learn from both success and failure (your own and other people's)

5.2 Sharing of the draft survey with the rest of the project partners

The designed draft of the questionnaires were sent to the alliance university partners to get their feedback about the survey improvement in September 2021. By the end of September 2021, the responses from the partners had been obtained, and the required amendments had been completed.

5.3 Results of the survey

The final questionnaires were prepared and distributed among the alliance university partners to conduct a survey with the target group (students and young researchers). The questionnaire ran from November 18, 2021, to February 15, 2022.

Figure 3 - Graphics with the results of participants in the survey

We can infer from Figure 3 that the survey mostly involved students and researchers from the University of Cadiz, followed by the University of Kiel and the University of Gdansk. Meanwhile, the researchers at the University of Split, the University of Malta, and the University of Western Brittany were less active. Moreover, the highest number of survey participants were PhD students (56%), followed by postdoctoral researchers (15%), assistant professors (15%), PhD candidates (13%), and 1% others.

Figure 4- Showing the participants' answers with the average rate of the survey

Figure 4 demonstrates that the factor "Into action" is associated with the highest score. This indicates that respondents to the survey perceive they have the most advantaged knowledge of entrepreneurship-related practical materials. Overall, survey results reveal that students have a relatively high level of knowledge, with values between 4 and 5. Whereas the factor "Into action" is followed by "Resources," "Ideas & Opportunities," "IP Protection and Practice," and "Entrepreneurial Tools." IP Protection and Practice as well as Entrepreneurial Tools were the fields with more difficult knowledge for the survey respondents.

More comprehensive questionnaire findings revealed the following information according to the factors:

• Into Actions – 4.0

The factor "Into Action" includes the following parameters in the order of participants' self-assessment of their understanding of the materials: working with others (4.29), taking initiative (4.17), learning through experience (4.00), coping with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk (3.85), and planning and management (3.72). This leads to the conclusion that the most required webinars should be focused on the areas of problem-solving (coping with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk), planning, and management.

• Resources – 3.74

The factor "Resources" includes the following parameters in their order of students understanding of the offered topics: motivation (4.36), self-awareness (3.93), mobilizing resources (3.61), mobilizing others (3.49), and financial literacy (3.34). The most important webinars must therefore be designed within the themes of financial literacy and resource mobilization, based on the poll's lowest-scoring respondents.

• Ideas and Opportunities – 3.72

The survey results demonstrated the following outcomes in order of the student's understanding of the materials: spotting opportunities (3.92), ethical and sustainable thinking (3.83), creativity (3.87), vision (3.54), and valuing ideas (3.46). Thus, we can clearly identify that the respondents have less knowledge of the themes of valuing ideas, vision, and creativity. As a result, the Spin-Off Competence webinars should be focused on the

aforementioned topics to enhance the alliance university students' business development skills.

• IP Protection and Practice (data from European IP Helpdesk) – 2.61

European
IPR Helpdesk

Data for the factor "IP Protection and Practice" were provided by the European IP Helpdesk. As a result, respondents to the surveys showed a relatively low level of understanding and knowledge on the topics of IP Practice (2.99) and IP Protection (2.24). Educational workshops and webinars should therefore include a focus on these topics to improve the knowledge and skills of young researchers in the Alliance.

• Entrepreneurial Tools (data from Santander Bank) – 2.14

The poll for the factor "Entrepreneurial Tools" was completed following a prior survey by Santander Bank. The survey results demonstrated that participants have the following level of knowledge in order of their understanding: knowledge about Design Thinking (2.25), knowledge of developing Business Model Canvas (2.20), understanding of Agile methodologies (2.11), and awareness of Lean Startups (2.00). Accordingly, as can be seen, respondents have a limited understanding of entrepreneurial tools. However, the most useful webinars can be prepared on the topics of Agile methodologies and Lean Startups.

5.4 Conclusions from the survey and design of the educative webinars:

The survey findings revealed a glaring discrepancy between the evaluation of the competencies integrated into the three areas of EntreComp and the assessment of IP Protection and Practice and Entrepreneurship Tools. In general, a medium level of knowledge and understanding of these materials is reflected by the researchers' overall rating of the EntreComp competencies, which is just above 3.5. In contrast, the variables for IP Protection and Practice, and Entrepreneurial Tools are less significant than the EntreComp parameters and, on average, equal 2.15.

Accordingly, the webinars of the Spin-Off Competence Lab should be developed in the following manner:

- Training should be aimed at covering the weakest EntreComp areas such as:
 - Differentiating between license types that can be used to protect rights and share ideas (2.89).
 - Capability to create business models based on their own ideas (3.02).
 - Making an effective pitch to prospective donors or investors. (3.12).
 - Acquiring and managing the resources required to put ideas into action (3.31).
 - Identifying public and private sources of funding for your own project (for example, prizes, crowdfunding, and shares) (3.18).

- Design of the webinars based on the survey provided by IP Helpdesk and Santander Bank. These trainings should be aimed to cover the following themes:
 - IP Protection and Practice
 - Agile Entrepreneurship
 - Design Thinking

6. CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED AND SOLUTIONS PROPOSED

- What have been the main difficulties you have faced in achieving the proposed objectives?

One of the issues was finding the specialists and covering all the identified fields of the survey, which are:

- Coping with uncertainty, ambiguity, and planning and management
- Mobilizing resources and financial literacy
- Thinking ethically and sustainably, creativity, vision, and valuing ideas
- IP Practice and IP Protection
- Business Model Canvas, Design Thinking, Business Model Canvas, Agile methodologies, and Lean Startups.

Finally, the following topics were covered:

- Intellectual Property Rights Trademarks Protection I, II
- Business model
- Speculative thinking I, II
- Skills to turn problems into opportunities and evolution methods using creative thinking methods
- Grant funding and equity finance
- Lean Startups - canvas methodology.

Another problem we encountered was the online execution of practical webinars with the alliance's university students and young researchers. Some webinars were postponed due to technical issues and then rescheduled without recording the practical completion of the tasks. However, the solution proposed was to record the theoretical parts of these webinars and upload the materials for these practical tasks to the SEA-EU website. In this manner, students and investigators who want to repeat the exercise may do so effortlessly. Moreover, interested researchers can communicate with the authors of our webinars to clarify their doubts. The example of these practical webinars can serve as "design thinking solving problems with new ideas" with theoretical and practical parts uploaded to the web page of SEA-EU. [Design Thinking – Solving Problems with new ideas – Kiel University – reSEArch-EU \(sea-eu.org\)](#)

- If you could start over with this action, what would you do differently?

The outcomes of the educational course developed by the Spin-Off Competence Laboratory have truly satisfied all the expectations and objectives. Any work, however, can be improved, especially after gaining professional experience. Thus, the following recommendations for improving ideas about the Spin-Off Competence Lab course can be applied in the future:

- Extension of the analysis of the target population: the initial survey at a more extended level (beyond the alliance universities) could provide additional insights into the training requirements of young researchers in Europe. This would enable us to offer the Spin-Off Competence Laboratory more effectively.
- Higher involvement of the alliance partners: Each alliance partner will strengthen the Spin-Off Competence Lab by developing an educational course that will provide both alliance researchers and international students free access to up-to-date essential knowledge on a variety of relevant topics including creative thinking, overcoming uncertainty, ambiguity, planning and management, financial literacy, creativity, vision, idea evaluation and other relevant topics.
- Speakers outside the alliance partners and Europe: The Spin-Off Competence Laboratory's curriculum could bring new insights from the addition of lecturers from outside the alliance universities and the European Union, such as those from the United States, South Korea, England, and other countries.
- Creation of freely accessible and helpful resources: Gathering materials pertinent to the establishment of businesses within the scientific community and making them freely available to young researchers could benefit them even more. Provide participants with extra resources, such as suggested readings, websites, tools, and templates, so they can continue learning and applying what they have learned. These resources ought to supplement the course material and assist students in continuing their entrepreneurial growth after the course.
- Designing evaluation and feedback tools: Create tests and quizzes to gauge participants' comprehension of the course material. Additionally, allow participants to receive feedback on their progress through assignments, peer reviews, or instructor comments.
- Participant engagement and support: Actively engage with participants throughout the course via discussion boards, interactive and live Q&A sessions, or email communication. Respond to their questions, provide answers, and build a friendly learning community.
- Assessment and advancement: Constantly gather participant input to gauge the course's efficacy. To improve the course's quality and impact, evaluate the feedback, spot areas that need work, and implement the appropriate changes.

7. RESULTS OBTAINED

- Which have been the main results obtained because of the Task where the referred action is included?

The main result of this deliverable was the creation of an educative course with free access to the Spin-Off Competence Laboratory - Spin-Off Competence Lab – reSEArch-EU (sea-eu.org)

Ten workshops were held:

1) 20 October 2022 -Lean StartUp

Description

Eric Ries' breakthrough lean canvas concept revolutionized the way businesses are created by allowing for quicker testing and iteration. It is also related to the notion of employing a more rigorous and empirical method, which is founded on assumptions to be tested as soon as feasible with the market. The webinar aimed to offer a substitute for the conventional business formation process, which is based on protracted, bureaucratic, and business plan-oriented methods.

The link to the video of the webinar:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wEeVgqrnGfc&t=1s>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 72, and the number of registered attendees was 143.

2) 24 January 2023 – Business model

The link to the video of the webinar:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y8oBeQJhLbw>

Additional resources:

<https://openvc.app/blog/startup-financial-model#>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 25, whereas the number of registered persons was 21.

Number of participant

3) 9 November 2022 - Grant-funding and equity finance

Description

To offset the losses that develop before the new business turns a profit, all start-ups will require early financing. It is typically impossible for start-ups to obtain debt financing from a bank because there is typically no revenue available to pay back the loan at the beginning of the business. The other primary choices, if the founders do not have personal finances available, are grant funding from government programs or equity financing from investors

who purchase shares in the company. The latter choice is challenging. Prof. Smith examined the online training curriculum that is accessible through this project and walk listeners

through the procedures that must be followed when applying for either type of startup funding.

The link to the video of the webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Laf8K5imCwM>

Participants

The total number of participants in the online webinar was 23, whilst the number of registered participants was 34.

Additional resources:

<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/grant-funding-and-equity-finance-russel/>

4) 11 November 2022 – Speculative design

Description

Since its rapid expansion in the twentieth century, design has primarily served as an unthinking support to industry and the applications of technology in our daily lives. We are witnessing a comeback of the concept that technology will be critical to our future survival in the current difficulties. Around 20 years ago, speculative design arose as a counter-approach to standard market-oriented design. For many years, SD was recognized (and criticized) for its propensity to generate future dystopias. As reality becomes more dystopian than fiction, it is critical to reconsider the role of speculative practice. The lecture will highlight the status of Speculative Design practice through personal projects and Speculative Education project experiences, as well as address potential future directions for the practice.

The link to the video of the webinar:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRG95DZmqDk&t=1s>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 32, while the number of registrants was 19.

5) 10 January 2023 – Speculative Design II

The link to the video of the webinar:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u_UPw-Y5N9Y&t=15s

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 19, while the number of registrants was 6.

Additional materials:

Download your FREE digital of the book: Beyond Speculative Design: Past – Present – Future (THE BOOK). Version in English [HERE!](#)

<https://speculativeedu.eu/>

6) 23 November 2022 - Skills to turn problems into opportunities and evaluation methods using creative thinking methods

Description

Setting up a new business endeavor is difficult, posing many attempt tests for the entrepreneurs. The ability to see things from diverse viewpoints via shifting perspectives becomes invariably important for the venture's existence. Delegates will learn about some of the elements of thinking and how they may be used to turn challenges into opportunities during this session. Evaluation approaches based on creative thinking will also be discussed.

The link to the video of the webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E46SjKdVbs0>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 66, while the number of registrants was 39.

7) 19 January 2023 – Intellectual Property Rights Patents (Part 1)

Description

The name of your company or the product you're releasing may be the most crucial choice you'll ever make. The Naming Group LLC's president and founder is Nina Beckhardt. How can you create a brand, what is intellectual property (IP), and how do you protect it, especially in the Metaverse? What is a patent, what is NFT and cryptocurrency, and how can I get one? Can I protect my brand name, logo, and other aspects of my business? What is legal to copy without breaking the law?

The legal protection of intellectual property (IP), which includes trademarks and inventions, grants a monopoly that has commercial advantages in terms of branding, a competitive edge in negotiations, generating income streams, and success in fact. It also plays a significant role in encouraging innovation and creativity.

Annual growth in the number of IP rights has been seen. IP rights are crucial for small businesses, individuals, and even large corporations. The session, which is separated into two parts, helps attendees grasp the fundamentals of what IP rights may protect.

The link to the video of the webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yhcX1R3KbE0>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 23, while the number of registered participants was 23.

8) 25 January 2023 - Intellectual Property Rights Trademarks protection (Part 2)

The link to the video of the webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LAKihRpySWQ>

Participants

The total number of participants in the webinar was 20, while the number of registrants was 18.

Number of participant

9-10) 4-6 July 2023 Design Thinking Solving problems with new ideas.

Description

Innovations occur where human desire, economic viability, and technological viability converge. While research and practice frequently place an emphasis on technical problem-solvability, this workshop prioritizes user requirements, which is the cornerstone of design thinking. Design Thinking is a methodical approach to solving complicated issues that uses the human perspective as the foundation for creating cutting-edge goods and services. Six distinct stages of the work process—understand, observe, point of view, ideate, prototype, and test—are completed iteratively by multidisciplinary teams.

We give you the tools you need to apply Design Thinking principles to your ideas or routine tasks in this class. You comprehend the fundamental tenets and key values of the Design Thinking methodology, as well as the six stages of the Design Thinking process, after the session is through. You will be able to use appropriate methodologies, like creative techniques, inside the Design Thinking process.

The link to the video of the webinar I: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WE6Eaa1ATSY>

The link to the video of the webinar II: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kQaPt38sUy4>

Participants

4 July

The total number of participants in the webinar was 52, while the number of registrants was 22.

Number of participantes

6 July

The total number of participants in the webinar was 27, while the number of registrants was 16.

Number of participantes

Additional materials:

<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/design-thinking-solving-problems-with-new-ideas-kiel-university/>

- How has this action been beneficial for the project partners individually?

We can highlight the following potential benefits:

- Virtual educative course in the entrepreneur field: The developed entrepreneurial course of the Spin Off Competence Laboratory is beneficial for each alliance partner because of free access to the virtual trainings with essential information and webinars on how to launch, run, and expand a business. The alliance young researchers can enrich their knowledge in business development and creative mindset in the convenient time for them.
- Opportunities for networking: Entrepreneurial courses frequently bring together people from various backgrounds building a beneficial network of like-minded entrepreneurs, mentors, and industry experts. Making connections throughout the course can lead to prospective partnerships, collaborations, and access to resources that will benefit the project partners both during and after the course.
- Access to resources: the Spin Off Competence Laboratory provides to the students' access to databases, literature, software tools, and other sources of information. These tools can help team members with critical duties like financial analysis, business model, and relevant topics.

- **Feedback from mentors:** there are opportunities for participants and students to receive feedback on their ideas, business plans, or clarify their doubts. Feedback may be provided by guest speakers; business holders and professors provided the webinars and workshops of the Spin Off Competence Laboratory.
- **Training to business mindset:** One of the intangible advantages of taking trainings in entrepreneurship is getting exposed to this thinking. The alliance researchers can pick up new skills including innovative thinking, spotting opportunities, and taking a proactive, problem-solving stance. This mentality change may have a good effect on their judgement, risk assessment, and general perspective of difficulties, ultimately promoting their own development and the advancement of the project.
- How has this action been beneficial for the consortium?

The beneficial sides of the Spin Off Competence Laboratory for the consortium are:

- **Increasing of the consortium universities reputation:** The design of a modern and demanding course for the alliance universities can increase the prestige of the consortium as well as each university, improve their reputation, draw in academics, and staff with talent, and forge solid relationships with the corporate/business world.
- **Fostering entrepreneurship and innovation:** By teaching students to think creatively, take calculated risks, and seek novel ideas, the course can help young researchers develop an entrepreneurial attitude. This may result in the emergence of companies and entrepreneurship among the university society.
- **Building of business partnerships:** The course can give consortium universities a place to work together with industry partners. These collaborations may lead to mentorship opportunities, industry experts giving guest lectures, internships, and even investment for promising start-up businesses. By encouraging information transfer and the real-world application of ideas, these partnerships can close the gap between academia and business.
- **Promoting interdisciplinary cooperation:** Entrepreneurship frequently calls for a multidisciplinary strategy, combining expertise from multiple sectors like business, technology, marketing, and design. The course can encourage a culture of teamwork and creativity by fostering interdisciplinary collaboration between students and instructors from various departments at the consortium universities.

8. QUALITY SELF-ASSESSMENT

- How could the results obtained be further exploited and sustained over time?

The sustainability of the developed tools and courses is provided by conserving them on the following platforms of the reSEArch-EU and SEA-EU projects:

- SEA Innovative Hub <https://sih.sea-eu.ug.edu.pl>

- Market place tool <https://marketplacetool.ug.edu.pl/marketplace-tool/>
- SEA Academy <https://academy.sea-eu.org/courses-2/>
- SEA-EU web page <https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/spin-off-competence-lab-2/?lang=es>
- YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wEeVgqrnGfc&list=PLMvtEOr--T7PeysXbh60naZWDmZM9JT2>